

Relation of Momentum/Energy Conservation to the Lorentz Transformation and Quantum Mechanics

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The Lorentz transformation (2x2) matrix is most easily derived for x, t for a particle with rest mass at rest at $x=0, t$. In the moving frame (constant $-v$) it moves with v and so $x'/t'=v$. This suggests that $x'=v g(v) t$ and $t'=g(v) t$. One may show that $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. A point we wish to make is that the notion of conservation of momentum, introduced in Newtonian nonrelativistic mechanics, does appear anywhere in this derivation. In previous notes, we often suggested in an ad hoc manner that this same Lorentz transformation should apply to (p, E) . Here, we argue that one may independently derive, using the variables p, E , the Lorentz transformation solely by considering motion v in the moving frame and conservation of momentum. To do so we consider a rest mass to consist of a photon bouncing back and forth. By viewing this system from a frame moving with constant $-v$ one may find a form for a Lorentz transformation which respects the $p/-p$ of the photon in both frames as that the average momentum in the moving frame is that same as that of a solid m_0 seen from the moving frame. We suggest that this implies the notion of conservation of momentum within the rest frame of the box holding the bouncing photon.

This begs the question: Why are two physical concepts (v and conservation of momentum) required for the variables $p-E$ and only one for $x-t$ in the derivation of the Lorentz transformation?

We argue that both physical concepts should apply to both sets of variables. This leads to the notion that $x-t$ must demonstrate conservation of momentum (and energy) which is something that does not happen in Newtonian mechanics.

A second consideration is the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$. This contains p, E and x, t and as argued above, both independently lead to the derivation of the Lorentz transformation. In the rest frame, one notices a peculiar antisymmetry if one only considers transformations of x, t points, i.e. x, t finite. In particular, $-m_0 c \Delta t$ changes value with Δt , but $p \Delta x$ ($p=0$) does not for finite Δx . We argue that there should be symmetry as there is no reason to expect Δt and Δx to be so different. This seems to lead to the notion of intervals Δt and Δx such that $-E \Delta t = 1$ and $p \Delta x = 1$. In other words, for $p \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta x \rightarrow$ infinite. In general, $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$. This leads to a different kind of physics from Newtonian, but two questions remain? First, where is the notion of conservation of momentum associated with $x-t$ and secondly, what physical reasons are there for $-E \Delta t = 1$ and $p \Delta x = 1$ being independent. We try to answer these two questions in this note.

Independent Derivations of the Lorentz Transformation for $x-t$ and $p-E$

The Lorentz transformation of special relativity is based on viewing particles/photons from different frames. A straightforward derivation of the Lorentz 2x2 matrix follows from considering a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0, t$. As viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$, one sees $v=x'/t'$. In other words, because $x=0, t=0$ map to $x'=0, t'=0$ under any 2x2 matrix, x' and t' must adjust to be consistent with a velocity v . This suggests the form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & g(v) \\ b & vg(v) \end{pmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

In previous notes, we have given arguments for $a = \gamma(v)$ and $b = \gamma(v)v$ and shown that $\gamma(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ so we do not repeat that here. The main point we wish to make is that the Lorentz matrix ((1)) may be derived only considering $x-t$ and using $x'/t' = v$. There is no need to consider the variables p, E or conservation of momentum, a concept from Newtonian mechanics. Given ((1)), we have suggested, in an ad hoc manner usually, in previous notes that it should also apply to p, E .

Here, we argue that ((1)) may be obtained independently through considerations of p, E , but this requires two conditions, not the single one of $v = x'/t'$ used for the $x-t$. The first consideration is that the particle with rest mass m_0 is moving with v . This is identical to the $x-t$ case (although one does not explicitly have x' or t'). The second condition, however, is that momentum (and energy are conserved). To see this second condition at work, we consider momentum here and imagine that m_0 may be created in two independent ways. The first involves a particle with rest mass m_{01} and momentum p bouncing back and forth in a box. The second involves a photon with momentum p doing the same.

The rest mass m_0 transforms as $\gamma(v)m_0$ as $p(\text{ave}) = 0$ in the rest frame. The overall momentum seen in the moving frame is $m_0 \gamma v$. For a photon, $E = pc$ from Maxwell's equations. If one considers for a photon $p = +$ or $-$, then:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p' \\ E' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1(v) & \gamma_2(v) \\ a & b \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p \\ |E| \end{pmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, $p' = \gamma_1(p = E) + \gamma_2 E$.

One must have $E' = p' c$, so $a = \gamma_2$ and $b = \gamma_1$ is a solution with $c = 1$, so $E' = \gamma_2 p + \gamma_1 E$ ((2b)) which maintains a transpose symmetry. For $-p$ one has:

$$p' = \gamma_1(-p = -E) + \gamma_2 E \quad \text{and} \quad E' = -\gamma_2 p + \gamma_1 E.$$

The average energy is: $\gamma_1 E$ which matches γm_0 above.

The average momentum is: $\gamma_2 E$. The average energy is $\gamma_1 E$. One must still have $E' = p' c$. This suggests $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2$. Thus, one obtains the Lorentz transformation again, but the question of momentum conservation has not been addressed. We argue that conservation of momentum is implicitly contained in the above calculation because in the rest frame one has m_0 (no net momentum, even though there is a photon bouncing back and forth). Thus, p and $-p$ cancel to leave an m_0 . The fact that m_0 transforms to $m_0 \gamma v$ and the average momentum for the photon p and $-p$ also gives the same overall momentum means that the p ($-p$) conservation still holds allowing for the creation of the new overall momentum. In other words, if one went into the rest frame of the system seen from the frame $-v$, one would again have p and $-p$. The Lorentz transformation ((2)) is consistent with this requirement.

In the above, v was introduced as a linear variable in the matrix because it is a linear variable in p for a particle with rest mass. If one considers a particle at rest, then the sign of momentum as seen in a frame, must come from the frame itself. This justifies the linear v in the matrix.

X-t, p-E and the Lorentz Transformation: How does Conservation of Momentum affect x-t?

In the above section, we argued that one may obtain the Lorentz matrix using the variables $x-t$ and the relation $x'/t'=v$ (i.e. a particle with rest mass, m_0 , is seen to move at speed v). Alternatively, one may use the variables $p-E$ and the two notions of motion v and conservation of momentum. This begs the question: Why should one require the physical law of conservation of momentum (from Newtonian mechanics) to derive the Lorentz transformation using $p-E$, but not for $x-t$? We suggest that for consistency, the notion of conservation of momentum should be directly linked to $x-t$, but given $x'=vt'$, one does not really see any idea of conservation of momentum for different v values. As a result, we suggest that some further analysis is required to find a link between $x-t$ and conservation of momentum.

Symmetry of Variables in Lorentz Invariants

We have argued above that one may obtain the Lorentz transformation independently for $x-t$ and $E-p$. This suggests that each set is as important as the other. Mathematically, one may find the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((3))$$

This applies to specific x, t points mapping to x', t' points. A problem, however, arises in the rest frame, one which we have mentioned in several previous notes, namely that $p=0$ means that $px=0$ for any finite x . Given that x, t are specific points which map to x', t' , we suggest considering intervals, i.e.

$$-E \Delta t + p \Delta x \quad ((4))$$

In the rest frame, a different Δt yields a different $E \Delta t$ product because $E = m_0 c^2$ is constant. The same consideration should hold for $p \Delta x$ because there should be a symmetry here. Any Δx , however, yields $p \Delta x = 0$ for $p = 0$. Thus, we suggest, as we have before, that:

$$P \rightarrow 0 \text{ means that } \Delta x \rightarrow \text{infinite such that } p \Delta x \rightarrow 1 \quad ((5))$$

This symmetry condition must then hold in other frames, i.e.

$$\Delta t = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((6))$$

Furthermore, $-E \Delta t$ and $p \Delta x$ are independent.

At this point, we suggest that one must determine physical consequences of the above suggestions as well as determine how conservation of momentum (and energy) applies to $x-t$. ((6)) implies specific regions in time and space which seem to have nothing to do with the trajectory $x'=vt'$. The trajectory implies that particles and photons move smoothly through x' in t' . It seems that ((6)) may represent resolutions. If this is the case, then $x'=vt'$ is not destroyed or completely independent, it is just that there are resolution restrictions. In other words, there is uncertainty in time and x . This seems to be associated with functions:

$$f_1(E,t), f_2(p,x) \quad ((7))$$

such that one observes the intervals ((6)), but at the same time has smooth motion through x,t . This seems like a paradox, and is, if one only uses ((7)). If one, however, uses $f_1^* f_1$ and $f_2^* f_2$ with:

$$f_1 = \exp(-iEt) \text{ and } f_2 = \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

Then $x'=vt'$ is validated through $f_1^* f_1 = 1$ and $f_2^* f_2 = 1$. At the same time f_1 and f_2 show the intervals ((6)). Given that $x'=vt'$ is an idealization in the sense that it does not show the resolution units directly, it seems consistent to have functions with more information than their modulus. In other words, the moduli of $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$ are 1 and only convey part of the overall information.

One may now see how conservation of momentum (and energy) are linked to $x-t$. If one considers $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$, then these are orthogonal functions. Thus, the product:

$$\int \exp(-ip_2x) \exp(ip_1x) dx \quad ((9))$$

may be used to evaluate conservation of momentum. If $p_1 = p_2$, then one loses all periodicity, while if $p_1 \neq p_2$, one does not, an integration over the period constant $|p_1 - p_2|$ may be used.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the 2x2 Lorentz transformation matrix may be obtained independently using the variable sets $x-t$ and $p-E$. In the first case, one only needs the notion of motion v in the moving frame as this directly influences $x'/t'=v$ because $x=0$, $t=0$ must transform to $x'=0$, $t'=0$ under any 2x2 matrix. One may derive the Lorentz transformation from this condition.

Alternatively, one may obtain the same transformation using the variables p,E , the notion of v and conservation of momentum/energy. In doing so, one considers a rest mass m_0 as consisting of a photon, with momentum p , moving back and forth in a box. As shown above, this leads to the same Lorentz transformation, but depends on the notion of conservation of momentum, we argue, in that p and $-p$ of the photon in the rest frame transform in such a way that one has m_0 in the rest frame and $\gamma m_0 v$ as momentum in the moving frame. Also, v in the Lorentz matrix allows for p and $-p$ for two different frames (v and $-v$) if one has a particle with

rest mass. As a result, we ask why conservation of momentum seems to be part of the p-E derivation of the Lorentz transformation and not the x-t derivation.

To analyse further, we consider the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$. Both p,E and x,t are equally valid because both sets may be used to derive the Lorentz transformation in the first place. Now, any x,t map to a set x',t', but we argue that an asymmetry exists in that in the rest frame, E delta t changes with values of delta t, but p delta x for p=0 and delta x finite does not. To create the required symmetry because (delta t and delta x should not behave differently) we suggest that as $p \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. This suggests that in various frames, $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$, i.e. that there are gradations. We argue that these are consistent with $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ functions such that $\exp(iEt)\exp(-iEt) = 1$ and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. These functions then show how conservation of energy and momentum become linked with x-t and not just p-E in the derivation of the Lorentz transformation.